

KOSTANECKI ROBINSON REACTION. PART III. BENZOYLATION OF ORCACETOPHENONE AND ITS MONOMETHYL ETHER.

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In continuation of the previous work orcacetophenone has been benzoylated giving 7-benzoyloxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone. This on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid gives 7-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone which on treatment with alcoholic potash gives 7-hydroxy-5-methylflavone. A noteworthy point is the new technique for the stepwise elimination of *O*-benzoyl group and the *C*-benzoyl group in the γ -pyrone ring.

In continuation of the previous work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 239, 487) orcacetophenone has been benzoylated. The reaction mixture after benzoylation is treated with petroleum ether and water to remove benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate respectively when a product (*A*), $C_{26}H_{30}O_5$, is obtained. This on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid gives an alkali-soluble product (*B*), $C_{23}H_{18}O_4$, which on treatment with alcoholic potash gives a product (*C*), $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$, with the loss of a benzoyl group. This product is 7-hydroxy-5-methylflavone (*I*, $R=R'=H$), prepared previously by Tambor (*Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 793) by the condensation of orcacetophenone dimethyl ether with methyl benzoate and subsequent ring-closure of the β -diketone. He records the m.p. 297° for the flavone and 115° for its methyl ether. Our m.ps., however, are 312° and $122-23^\circ$ respectively.

Thus the product (*A*), which is 7-benzoyloxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone (*I*, $R=R'=COPh$), gives on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid the product (*B*), 7-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone (*I*, $R=H$; $R'=COPh$), which on treatment with alcoholic potash gives 7-hydroxy-5-methylflavone of Tambor (*loc. cit.*).

The monomethyl ether of orcacetophenone on similar benzoylation and subsequent treatment of the reaction product with petroleum ether and water gives 7-methoxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone, identical with the methyl ether of (*I*, $R=H$; $R'=COPh$). This on treatment with alcoholic potash gives 7-methoxy-5-methylflavone, identical with the methyl ether of (*I*, $R=R'=H$).

The procedure generally adopted in working up the product obtained on the aroylation of *o*-hydroxy-ketones is the treatment of the reaction mixture with alcoholic potash. This leads generally to the removal of both the *O*-aroyl group and the *C*-aroyl group in the pyrone ring and the 3-aroylflavones are not generally capable of isolation. Some workers have,

however, been able in a few cases to isolate 3-benzoylflavones by modifications of the usual procedure of working up the reaction products or changing the conditions of reaction (Aigar, McCarthy and Dick, *Proc. Roy. Irish Acad.*, 1933, **41B**, 155; Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1381; Sugawara, *ibid.*, 1934, 1483, Rangaswami and Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1939, **10A**, 6).

The experimental technique, followed here, of treating the reaction mixture after benzylation with petroleum ether and water, to remove benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate respectively can be of great value in the isolation of flavones with both the *O*- and the *C*-benzoyl groups intact. The *O*-benzoyl group can be then smoothly removed by the use of concentrated sulphuric acid leaving the 3-benzoyl group intact. The method promises to be of general use and preliminary experiments with other *o*-hydroxy-ketones justify this expectation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Benzylation of Orcacetophenone: 7-Benzoyloxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone (I, R=R'=COPh).—Orcacetophenone (5 g.), sodium benzoate (15 g.) and benzoic anhydride (50 g.) were heated in a 250 c.c. round-bottomed flask in an oil-bath at 180-190° for 8 hours. The compact mass obtained was ground up and refluxed repeatedly with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and filtered each time till the benzoic anhydride was removed. The product was dried and then ground up with excess of water to remove sodium benzoate. The residue was then crystallised from rectified spirit in slender shining needles (4 g.), m. p. 172-73°. The product is insoluble in alkali and gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 78.0; H, 4.4. C₃₀H₂₆O₅ requires C, 78.3; H, 4.3 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone (I, R=H; R'=COPh).—The above condensation product (I, R=R'=COPh; 2 g.) was shaken up with concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) and kept for 4 hours. The product, obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water, was crystallised from rectified spirit in rectangular prisms (1 g.), m.p., 282-83°. The product is soluble in caustic alkalis without any fluorescence. It also gives no fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 4.8. C₂₈H₁₈O₄ requires C, 77.5; H, 4.5 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, was crystallised from alcohol in rectangular prisms, m.p. 171-73°. (Found : C, 75.0; H, 4.7. $C_{25}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 75.4; H, 4.5 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared as usual with potassium carbonate and methyl iodide, was crystallised from rectified spirit in clusters of tiny needles, m.p. 186-87°. (Found : C, 77.6; H, 5.0. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 77.8; H, 4.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-5-methylflavone.—Debenzoylation did not take place on keeping 7-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone with 10% sodium hydroxide for 60 hours. It was, however, effected by heating the benzoyl derivative with alcoholic potash. 7-Hydroxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (10%; 25 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The excess of alcohol was distilled over and the reaction mixture acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 312°. Tambor (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 297°. The product gives bluish fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid and caustic alkalis. (Found : C, 76.1; H, 4.7. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 75.2; H, 4.8 per cent).

7-Benzoyloxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone was similarly debenzoylated to 7-hydroxy-5-methylflavone.

7-Methoxy-5-methylflavone, prepared with dimethyl sulphate and alkali, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 122-23°. Tambor (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 115°.

Benzoylation of Orcacetophenone Monomethyl Ether : 7-Methoxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone.—Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (2 g.), sodium benzoate (6 g.) and benzoic anhydride (20 g.) were heated for 7 hours at 180-90°. The product, obtained on treatment with petroleum ether and water as above, was crystallised from rectified spirit in clusters of tiny needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 186-87°. Mixed m.p. with the methyl ether of 7-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-5-methylflavone, described before, was not depressed.

On refluxing with alcoholic potash 7-methoxy-5-methylflavone was obtained as shown by direct comparison with the same.

Further work on the application of this method for the isolation of 3-aroxy-flavones is in progress. Experiments are also in progress to investigate the use of various other solvents in place of petroleum ether. All the analyses are microanalyses.

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